

ANNUAL REPORT ON MNCH INDICATOR APPLICATION 1

Deliverable 4.2

Annual report on MNCH indicator application 1

HIGH HORIZONS – D4.2

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition/Description
ASL Roma	Regional health service in Lazio (Italy)
CCHI	Climate change and health indicator
CDC	Centres for Disease Control and Prevention
CeSHHAR	Centre for Sexual Health and HIV/AIDS Research (Zimbabwe)
CFC	Chlorofluorocarbon
CSTE	Council of State and Territorial Epidemiologists
DHS	Demographic and Health Survey
DPSEEA	Driving Force-Pressure-State-Exposure-Effect-Action
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium Range Weather Forecasts
EEA	European Environment Agency
EMS	Emergency Medical Services
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency (United States of America)
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GÖG	Gesundheit Österreich GmbH (= Austrian National Public Health Institute)
ID	Identification
LSE	London School of Economics (United Kingdom)
MNCH	Maternal, newborn and child health
UGRAZ	University of Graz (Austria)
UK	United Kingdom
UN	United Nations
USA	United States of America
WHO	World Health Organization
WHO/CCH	World Health Organization Department of Climate Change and Health
WHO/MCA	World Health Organization Department of Maternal, Newborn, Child and Adolescent Health and Ageing
Wits RHI	Research institute of the University of the Witwatersrand (South Africa)
WP	Work package

Executive summary

This deliverable reports the first annual report on maternal, newborn and child health (MNCH) indicator application. It focuses on the broader climate and health indicator landscape before highlighting maternal, newborn and child health and climate indicators in some of the countries covered by the HIGH Horizons project.

In terms of indicators, it reports on global, regional and national climate and health indicators that already exist. It also highlights opportunities for the identification of MNCH heat indicators from existing climate indicators and health indicators. In addition, it focuses on the governance structure behind the creation and monitoring of climate and health indicators and how this can be used to aid the effective implementation of operational climate and health including MNCH indicators in countries.

We will build on this work in the next annual report which will be delivered in August 2025 and in the final report in August 2026.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This document provides an overview of the environment and health analysis that has taken place for deliverable D4.2 and builds on the work in D4.1, the report on the national workshops held in South Africa and Zimbabwe to discuss heat-health indicators (Brimicombe et al., 2024b). It provides an overview of types of climate change and health indicators, operational monitoring processes and examples of new indicators that could be monitored for maternal, newborn and child health (MNCH) and heat.

1.2 Relation to other project work

This deliverable influences the direction of the project for the next years. It provides key information across the work packages of WP2, 3 and 4. Some of the notable connections are:

- D3.1 Expert Group established and operational (April 2023)¹
- D3.2 Methods for selection of indicators (February 2024)¹
- D3.3 [Report on predictive heat warning thresholds](#) (February 2024)
- D4.1 National indicators to discuss heat-health indicators (April 2024)²
- D2.4 Heat-health analysis report 2 (due August 2025)
- D4.3 Annual report on MNCH indicator application 2 (due August 2025).

¹ The establishment of the Expert Group and their scoping meeting in April 2024 are clearly described in: [Report of a scoping meeting for the selection of indicators to monitor the impact of extreme heat on maternal, newborn and child health](#), Geneva, Switzerland, 24-25 April 2023. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2024. Licence: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO.

² This deliverable is under review and is expected to be approved at the latest in December 2025. The metadata of this report have already been deposited in Zenodo: Brimicombe, C., Madondo, C., Portela, A., Jackson, D., Mutasa, C., Machingura, F., & HIGH Horizons Study Group. (2024b). [HIGH Horizons - National Workshops to Discuss Heat-Health Indicators](#). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13347891>

1.3 Structure of the document

This document has seven main chapters. First an overview of the background of the importance of climate and health indicators and indicator creation on the HIGH Horizons project in Chapter 2. Then, the methodology of the mapping is outlined in Chapter 3. Next, global, regional and national climate change and health indicators are explored Chapter 4. In Chapter 5, examples of climate change and maternal, newborn and child health indicators are focused on. The discussion and links with the wider body of literature are outlined in Chapter 6, a summary of key findings is in Chapter 7, before concluding in Chapter 8.

2 Background

Climate Change and Health Indicators (CCHIs) are crucial quantitative measures designed to monitor, track, and communicate the impacts of climate change on human health. These indicators play a significant role in supporting decision-making processes for developing, evaluating, and implementing intervention strategies and plans (Di Napoli et al., 2022).

Several conceptual frameworks have been developed to systematically categorise and understand the relationships between climate change and health outcomes, and these frameworks can be used to support the identification of indicators. One recognised framework is the Driving Force-Pressure-State-Exposure-Effect-Action (DPSEEA). Developed by the World Health Organization (WHO) in 2001 and identified by Hambling et al. (2011), the DPSEEA framework outlines the causal chain linking climate change to adverse health outcomes. It starts with driving forces such as population growth, energy consumption, and agricultural practices. These driving forces create pressures, including emissions of greenhouse gases (GHGs), aerosols, and chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs), which alter the state of the climate system, reflecting long-term changes. These changes lead to specific climate-related exposures for individuals, such as heatwaves, cold waves, flooding, and drought. These exposures result in health outcomes, including cardiovascular

diseases and acute and chronic respiratory diseases. Finally, actions such as international and national policies and hazard management strategies are implemented in response (WHO, 2001; Boylan et al., 2018; Balbus et al., 2016; Di Napoli et al., 2022).

Another framework proposed by Liu et al. (2021) incorporates population vulnerabilities, emphasising the need to consider how different populations are disproportionately affected by climate change due to factors such as age, socioeconomic status, and pre-existing health conditions. This framework highlights the importance of understanding the differential impacts on vulnerable groups to tailor interventions effectively (Liu et al., 2021). In addition, in HIGH Horizons, a conceptual framework was developed to highlight the pathways whereby heat influences certain health outcomes. This framework was made publicly available on the project website³ and goes on to inform the selection of CCHIs for MNCH outcomes.

Recent research highlights the necessity for a comprehensive set of CCHIs to monitor and address the health impacts of climate change effectively. A scoping review conducted by the UK Health Security Agency in 2023 highlights the need for diverse indicators encompassing exposure, vulnerability, outcome, and action/process metrics. Additionally, Ebi et al. (2021) recommends including indicators related to health system impacts, adaptation processes, and health system resilience, providing a holistic understanding of climate change effects on health (Ebi et al., 2021; UK Health Security Agency 2023).

The HIGH Horizons project focuses amongst other objectives on the selection of global heat-health indicators for monitoring impact of heat on maternal, newborn and child health. To date on the project the WHO has organised an expert group

³ See [Conceptual framework on extreme heat and maternal, newborn and child health – HIGH Horizons \(high-horizons.eu\)](https://high-horizons.eu). The framework is also described in the scoping meeting report of the Expert Group (WHO, 2024).

meeting in-person and two online meetings towards the selection of global maternal, newborn and child health indicators that monitor the impact of extreme heat (WHO, 2024). In addition, WHO is extracting content of national heat health plans to identify existing content that relates to MNCH including activities, indicators and key messages. The extraction findings complement this report by drawing from the global policy base and identifying gaps that have occurred, and will be reported in HIGH Horizons deliverable 4.3 due in August 2025. HIGH Horizons also organised two in-country workshops in South Africa and Zimbabwe in January 2024 to present important data related to the impact of heat on MNCH and start discussions on the selection of national indicators that monitor the impact of heat on MNCH.⁴

In this study, we support the ongoing work of the selection of indicators tracking the heat impact on MNCH. We do this by building on the work of a climate and health indicator mapping carried out by the Lancet Countdown for Climate Change and Health in 2020 to assess from literature the global picture for climate change and health indicators. In addition, we use the expertise of the partners on the HIGH Horizons project to evaluate CCHIs for their contexts. We answer the questions:

- 1) What is the extent to which climate and health indicators respectively are already being monitored by countries?*
- 2) Are there any climate or health indicators that could easily be transformed into climate change and health indicators?*
- 3) What is the governance structure and who is involved in the selection of climate change and health indicators?*

⁴ Findings are described in deliverable D4.1 which is expected to be approved at the latest in December 2025. See Brimicombe et al. (2024b).

3 Methods

3.1 Mapping of global climate change and health indicators

To compile and categorise climate change and health indicators for this report, a comprehensive mapping of multiple sources was conducted to gather relevant data. The sources included peer-reviewed scientific literature and grey literature including reports from international and national health agencies, and initiatives focused on climate change and health. The search was conducted using academic databases such as Scopus and Google Scholar, as well as through direct access to reports, websites and publications from organisations actively monitoring climate change impacts on health. The first search was carried out in September 2020 by Chloe Brimicombe and Claudia Di Napoli and reviewed by Elizabeth Robinson for the Lancet Countdown for Climate Change and Health Working Group 1. This search was updated in July 2024 by Katherina Wieser and Tobias Monthaler from HIGH Horizons partner UGRAZ.

The search results were mapped in a table including information on the Initiative Name, Provider, Geographical Area of Coverage, Climate Change and Health Indicators, Frequency of Updates, Time Period of Coverage and End-Users.

Each identified indicator was then reviewed and categorised based on its primary focus and intended use within the context of climate change and health. The categorisation process involved identifying common themes and attributes among indicators to classify them into distinct categories. This classification was guided by conceptual frameworks proposed in the literature, including the Driving Force-Pressure-State-Exposure-Effect-Action framework by the WHO and other relevant frameworks emphasising exposure, vulnerability, health outcomes, and adaptation measures.

Based on this, indicators were organised into five *categories*: Health Outcomes, Climate Exposure, Environmental Quality, Vulnerability and Adaptation. Furthermore, a categorisation into a range of specific *domains* was performed such as Heat-Related Indicators, Air Quality Indicators, Flood-Related Indicators, Vector-Borne Diseases, Infectious Diseases, Water and Food Borne Diseases, Mental Health and Other Health Impacts, Noise Pollution Indicators, Environmental and Ecosystem Changes, and Wildfire and Forest Fire Indicators.

3.2 Mapping of national climate change and MNCH indicators

To support efforts for the global mapping of the global climate change and health indicators we asked partners and collaborators of the HIGH Horizons project to fill out information on climate change, and MNCH indicators for their countries. The template for this can be found in Annex.

The request was sent to HIGH Horizons partners in Greece, Italy, Kenya, South Africa, Sweden and Zimbabwe, and to external collaborators in Austria, Finland and Uruguay. The three latter countries have been included because our heat-health data analysis will be geographically expanded potentially using their national datasets (see D2.3; Brimicombe et al., 2024a). Updated results of the health outcome analysis will be described in HIGH Horizons deliverable 2.4, due in August 2025.

4 Climate change and health monitoring initiatives

This section explores various initiatives and frameworks dedicated to understanding and mitigating the health impacts of climate change. Resulting from the mapping exercise of global climate change and health indicators, Table 1 provides an overview of various climate change and health initiatives, their providers, geographical areas of focus, and key descriptions of their activities.

Global initiatives like the Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project and The Lancet Countdown provide comprehensive data on heat exposure, extreme weather, and food security.

The Lancet Countdown, established in 2016, tracks progress on health and climate change, developing and annually updating a set of indicators on a global 0.75x0.75 grid level and publishes regular reports for countries across Europe, South America, Japan, and China. These indicators focus on health impacts, exposures, and vulnerabilities associated with climate change (Cai et al., 2023; Di Napoli et al., 2022; Moran et al., 2022; Romanello et al., 2023).

Various national and regional agencies have also developed their own sets of CCHIs tailored to their specific contexts. For instance, the United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) tracks indicators such as heat-related deaths and illnesses, air quality, and vector-borne diseases. The Australian Institute of Health and Welfare monitors indicators related to heat-related risks, air quality, and exposure to extreme weather events. The Korea Disease Control and Prevention Agency focuses on heat waves, cold waves, air quality, and infectious diseases, while the Environmental Health Intelligence New Zealand tracks notifications of cryptosporidiosis, giardiasis, and salmonellosis, along with temperature extremes and soil moisture deficits (US EPA 2024; Australian Institute of Health and Welfare 2024; Kim et al., 2022; Massey University 2024).

For Europe, initiatives such as the European Environment Agency climate indicators, the European Climate and Health Observatory, and Climate-ADAPT track a range of indicators including air pollution, extreme temperatures, and floods, with updates occurring every few years. In the UK, the Climate Change Committee focuses on heat stress, air quality, and the vulnerability of healthcare infrastructure. The USA hosts several initiatives like the National Environmental Health Tracking Climate Change Indicators and the Climate Change: Society and Health Indicators by the EPA, which monitor heat stress, air quality, and vector-

borne diseases on a state and district scale. Sub-national initiatives like the Washington Tracking Network and California's Climate Change & Health Vulnerability Indicators emphasise local issues such as drought, flood risk, and sea level rise. Internationally, the Medical Journal of Australia and Environmental Health Indicators New Zealand address country-specific concerns like heat-related risks and water-borne diseases.

Table 1: Climate change and health monitoring initiatives

Initiative	Provider	Geographical Area	Description
European Environment Agency Climate	European Environment Agency (EEA)	Europe	Tracks indicators like air pollution, extreme temperatures, floods, and more. Updated mostly every 4 years. Last major update in 2024.
Climate-ADAPT	European Environment Agency and European Commission	Europe	Tracks indicators from EEA Climate Indicators plus additional data from Copernicus and Lancet Countdown.
Climate Change Committee Indicators	Climate Change Committee	UK	Focuses on heat stress, air quality, and vulnerability of healthcare infrastructure.
National Environmental Health Tracking Climate Change Indicators	Centres for Disease Control and Prevention	USA (Data not always available for all states)	Includes indicators like heat stress, flood vulnerability, and air quality. Indicators have varying update frequencies.
Climate Change: Society and Health Indicators	United States Environmental Protection Agency	USA, Census/District Scale	Focuses on heat-related illnesses and deaths, air quality, and vector-borne diseases. Updates resumed in 2024.
State Environmental Health Indicators Collaborative (SEHIC) Climate and Health Indicators	Council of State and Territorial Epidemiologists	USA, Census/District Scale	Tracks heat-related deaths and illnesses, extreme weather events, and vector-borne diseases. Last updates mostly in 2018.
Washington Tracking Network	Washington State Department of Health	Washington State, USA, Census/District Scale	Covers air quality, drought, flood risk, snowpack, and more. Recent updates in 2021 and 2024.
Climate Change & Health Vulnerability Indicators for California	California Department of Public Health	California, USA, Census/District Scale	Tracks extreme heat, air quality, wildfires, and sea level rise. Allows combination with vulnerability indicators. Recent updates in 2024.

Initiative	Provider	Geographical Area	Description
Minnesota Environmental Health Indicators	Minnesota Public Health Department	Minnesota, USA, Census/District Scale	Tracks extreme heat and air pollution. Includes projections under different climate scenarios. No recent updates.
Medical Journal of Australia (MJA) Climate Change and Health Indicators	MJA Lancet Countdown	Australia, Country Level	Focuses on heat-related risks, labour capacity, mental health, and wildfire exposure. Recent updates in 2024.
Environmental Health Indicators New Zealand	Massey University	New Zealand, District Scale	Tracks water-borne diseases, temperature extremes, and soil moisture. Recent updates in 2024.
The Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project	Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research and IIASA	Global, 0.5x0.5 grid	Models air quality, labour productivity, temperature-related mortality, and water-borne diseases.
The Lancet Countdown Climate and Health Indicators	The Lancet Countdown	Global, 0.75x0.75 grid, Country-level	Tracks heat exposure, extreme weather events, food security, and vector-borne diseases. Updated annually.
National Climate Health Impact Assessment in the Republic of Korea	Korea Disease Control and Prevention Agency	Korea	Includes heat waves, cold waves, air quality, and infectious diseases. Updated annually starting from various years.

4.1 Climate change and health indicators by category and domain

This section provides an overview of the current CCHIs available through the initiatives discussed in the preceding chapter 3.1. In total 55 indicators were identified which can be organised into the following

- (1) *categories*: Health Outcomes, Climate Exposure, Environmental Quality, Vulnerability and Adaptation
- (2) *domains*: Heat-Related Indicators, Air Quality Indicators, Flood-Related Indicators, Vector-Borne Diseases, Infectious Diseases, Water and Food Borne Diseases, Mental Health and Other Health Impacts, Noise Pollution Indicators, Environmental and Ecosystem Changes, and Wildfire and Forest Fire Indicators.

The categories of indicators found across the initiatives are outlined in **Error! Reference source not found.1**.

Figure 1: Overview of (categories of) indicators in climate change and health initiatives

As shown in Figure 2 heat-related indicators and air quality indicators are the most frequently monitored, highlighting their critical importance in climate change

studies. Other categories, such as flood-related indicators, vector-borne diseases, and infectious diseases, also receive notable attention.

Figure 2: Frequency of climate change and health indicator categories

4.2 Heat and MNCH indicators

Heat and health indicators recorded by the mapped initiatives in chapter 3.1 include measures of heat-related mortality, morbidity, temperature exposure and impact, heat impact on activities, and mental health effects. The frequency of updates for these indicators varies, with some being updated annually, while others are updated less frequently. The initiatives span across regions such as Europe, the USA, Australia, New Zealand, and Korea, involving organisations like the European Environment Agency, the Centres for Disease Control and Prevention, the Lancet Countdown, and national health departments.

Table 2 provides a comprehensive overview of heat-related indicators categorised by different initiatives and providers across various geographical areas. It highlights a range of metrics used to monitor the impacts of heat on public health and the environment.

Table 2: Heat and health indicators

Initiative	Rate of heat deaths, hospitalisations, and ER visits	Heat-related mortality	Heat-related illnesses	Heat stress indicators	Heat impact on physical and sporting activities	Mental health impacts following severe weather	Cold wave impacts and related health outcomes
European Climate and Health Observatory	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	
National Environmental Health Tracking Climate Change Indicators (CDC)	✓	✓	✓	✓			
State Environmental Health Indicators Collaborative (CSTE)	✓	✓	✓				
Washington Tracking Network	✓		✓	✓			
Climate Change & Health Vulnerability Indicators for California	✓		✓	✓	✓		
Minnesota Environmental Health Indicators		✓	✓	✓			
Medical Journal of Australia Climate Change and Health Indicators	✓		✓	✓	✓		
National Climate Health Impact Assessment in Korea	✓	✓		✓			✓
Lancet Countdown	✓	✓		✓	✓		

The indicators can be categorised into: Temperature Exposure and Impact, Heat-Related Mortality, Heat-Related Morbidity, Heat Impacts on Activities and Mental Health. As shown in Figure 3 Rate of heat deaths, hospitalisations, and ER visits is the most frequently mentioned category closely followed by heat-related mortality and heat-related illnesses. Heat Impact on Activities is noted four times while Mental Health indicators related to heat appear twice.

Figure 3: Frequency of heat-related indicator categories

5 National operational monitoring

Based on our country-level mapping (see chapter 3.2) we observe that within countries, there are different approaches for how health indicators and climate indicators are monitored. This is also the case for heat-related and maternal, Newborn and child health indicators.

Out of HIGH Horizons partners and collaborators asked, three contributed answers (n = 3 / 9), with information from Zimbabwe and South Africa collected during the national workshops⁵ (n = 5 / 9).

The country responses from Austria, Finland, Italy, Zimbabwe and South Africa can be seen below. What was apparent was that many researchers were not familiar with the climate and health indicators in their country and the governance structure behind it, and this may also explain why we did not receive response from all countries.

⁵ The findings are described in deliverable D4.1 which we expect to be approved in December 2025. See Brimicombe et al. (2024b).

5.1 Austria

❖ Climate indicators

Table 3: Climate indicators, Austria

Name of indicator (i.e. heatwave)	Definition	Unit of measure	Coverage in the country (i.e. local, regional, country level)
Extremely hot days	# of days with max. temperature ≥ 35 °C per year	Count	1x1 km grid
Heat days	# of days with max. temperature ≥ 30 °C per year	Count	1x1 km grid
Tropical nights	# of night with min. temperature ≥ 20 °C per year	Count	1x1 km grid
Summer days	# of days with max. temperature ≥ 25 °C per year	Count	1x1 km grid
Average summer temperature	average temperature in June, July & August	°C	1x1 km grid

- **Departments and Stakeholders who decide on indicators:** GeoSphere Austria (Austrian official weather service)
- **How often are indicators updated:** Regularly (when new information comes to light)
- **How are new indicators suggested:** based on international literature

❖ Maternal, newborn and child health indicators

Table 4: MNCH indicators, Austria

Name of indicator (i.e. heatwave)	Definition	Unit of measure	Coverage in the country (i.e. local, regional, country level)
Stillbirths	Percentage of stillbirths in total births	%	Regional (district level)
Caesarean rate	Percentage of c-sections in total births	%	Regional (district level)
Birth weight	Average weight of newborns	G	Regional (district level)
APGAR score	Median APGAR score of newborns	levels 1-10	Regional (district level)

Further indicators see: <https://www.statistik.at/en/statistics/population-and-society/population/births/medical-and-socio-medical-characteristics-of-newborns>

❖ **Climate change and health indicators**

Climate change and health indicators have been suggested in a new report by the public health department. These are based upon those already monitored in the Lancet Countdown for Climate and Health.

5.2 Finland

❖ **Climate indicators**

The Finnish Meteorological Institute has several indicators. The indicators for heat and cold waves are defined here <https://en.ilmatieteenlaitos.fi/warnings-on-hot-and-cold-weather>. Air quality index: <https://en.ilmatieteenlaitos.fi/air-quality>

- **Departments and Stakeholders who decide on indicators:** Finnish Meteorological Institute

❖ **Maternal, newborn and child health indicators**

Finland has an excellent coverage of multiple national registers, where individuals can be linked using a unique ID code given to all permanent residents. Many indicators can be calculated from there. Some examples:

- Medical birth register: <https://thl.fi/en/statistics-and-data/data-and-services/register-descriptions/newborns> and related perinatal statistics: <https://thl.fi/en/statistics-and-data/statistics-by-topic/sexual-and-reproductive-health/parturients-deliveries-and-births/perinatal-statistics-parturients-delivers-and-newborns>
- Causes of death statistics: <https://stat.fi/en/statistics/ksyyt>, and related releases: <https://stat.fi/en/statistics/ksyyt#pastPublications>

- Statistics on births: <https://stat.fi/en/statistics/synt> and related releases: <https://stat.fi/en/statistics/synt#pastPublications>

- **Departments and Stakeholders who decide on indicators:** Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (Medical Birth Register), Statistics Finland (causes of death), Digital and Population Data Services Agency (population statistics)

❖ **Climate change and health indicators**

It was unclear from our research whether the CCHIs are being monitored yet in Finland.

5.3 Italy

❖ **Climate indicators**

Table 5: Climate indicators, Italy

Name of indicator (i.e. heatwave)	Definition	Unit of measure	Coverage in the country (i.e. local, regional, country level)
Daily temperature	Estimated daily temperature values from spatio-temporal models*	°C	1x1 km grid
Heat days	# of days with maximum apparent temperature > specific heat-health thresholds defined for each city (within the Italian Heat Health Watch Warning System, active from May to September)	Count	City level (27 cities)

Note: The models are updated until 2015.

- **Departments and Stakeholders who decide on indicators:** Ministry of Health, Italian Civil Protection, Department of Epidemiology of Lazio Region
- **How often are indicators updated:** Regularly during summer period (heat days)

❖ Maternal, newborn and child health indicators

Table 6: MNCH indicators, Italy

Name of indicator (i.e. heatwave)	Definition	Unit of measure	Coverage in the country (i.e. local, regional, country level)
Births	New births per year	Count	Municipality level
Preterm births	22-36 weeks of gestation	count / raw rate	Municipality level (rate: district level)
Low birth weight	weight <2500g	count / raw rate	Municipality level (rate: district level)
Twin births		count / raw rate	Municipality level (rate: district level)
Congenital malformations	Malformations defined by ICD9-CM 740-759	count / raw rate	Municipality level (rate: district level)
Early neonatal mortality	0-7 days	count / raw rate	Municipality level (rate: district level)
Neonatal mortality	0-28 days	count / raw rate	Municipality level (rate: district level)
Infant mortality	0-365 days	count / raw rate	Municipality level (rate: district level)

Further information available in Italian: https://www.opensalutelazio.it/salute/stato_salute.php?materno

- **Departments and Stakeholders who decide on indicators:** Department of Epidemiology of Lazio Region
- **How often are indicators updated:** Annually

❖ Climate change and health indicators

It was unclear from our research whether the CCHIs are being monitored yet in Lazio or Italy.

5.4 Zimbabwe

This information comes from Deliverable 4.1 (Brimicombe et al., 2024b), which describes the indicators being monitored in Zimbabwe.

❖ Climate indicators

Table 7: Climate indicators, Zimbabwe

Indicator	Definition	Frequency	Coverage
Max, min and average temperature	Max, min and average temperature in degrees Celsius	3 times a day	Whole country
Heatwave frequency	3 or more days of above average temperatures.	When a heatwave occurs	Whole country
Duration of the heatwave	3 or more days of above average temperatures.	When a heatwave occurs	Whole country
Number of hot days	Number of days above 35°C	Daily	Whole country

- **Departments and Stakeholders who decide on indicators:** Department of Meteorology.

❖ Maternal, newborn and child health indicators

Table 8: MNCH indicators, Zimbabwe

Indicator	Definition	Frequency	Coverage
Live births at hospital	Live birth of a baby in a healthcare facility	Weekly, Monthly, Quarterly and Annually	Whole country
Live births at home	Live birth of a baby in a home setting	Weekly, Monthly, Quarterly and Annually	Whole country
Low birth weight	weight <2500g	Weekly, Monthly, Quarterly and Annually	Whole country
Child deaths	Mortality in the under 5s	Weekly, Monthly, Quarterly and Annually	Whole country
Neonatal deaths	Mortality in babies between 1 and 28 days old.	Weekly, Monthly, Quarterly and Annually	Whole country
Stillbirths	the birth of an infant that has died in the womb, after having survived through at least the first 28 weeks of pregnancy.	Weekly, Monthly, Quarterly and Annually	Whole country

- **Departments and Stakeholders who decide on indicators:** Ministry of Health and the Demographic Health Surveillance surveys.
- **Frequency updated:** Alongside updates to the rounds in the Demographic and Health Surveys (DHS) and [DHIS2](#).

❖ Climate change and health indicators

A climate and health working group has been established in Zimbabwe since the HIGH Horizons indicator workshop in January 2024. It is hoped that this can help lead to the creation of heat and MNCH indicators, as well as other CCHI.

5.5 South Africa

This information comes from Deliverable 4.1 (Brimicombe et al., 2024b), which describes the indicators being monitored in South Africa.

❖ Climate indicators

Table 9: Climate indicators, South Africa

Indicator	Definition	Frequency	Coverage
Frost Days	Number of days when TN < 0 °C	Daily	Whole country
TN below 2°C	Number of days when TN < 2 °C	Daily	Whole country
Max TX	Warmest daily TX	Daily	Whole country
Min TN	Coldest daily TN	Daily	Whole country
Warm spell duration indicator	Annual number of days contributing to events where 6 or more consecutive days experience TX > 90th percentile	Seasonal	Whole country
Cold spell duration indicator	Annual number of days contributing to events where 6 or more consecutive days experience TN < 10th percentile	Annual	Whole country
Fraction of days with temperatures above the median	Percentage of days where TX > 50th percentile	Seasonal	Whole country
TX of at least 30°C	Number of days when TX >= 30 °C	Seasonal	Whole country

Indicator	Definition	Frequency	Coverage
User-defined consecutive number of hot days and nights	Annual count of d consecutive days where both TX > 95th percentile and TN > 95th percentile, where $10 \geq d \geq 2$	Annual	Whole country
Max TN	Warmest daily TN	Annual	Whole country
Min TX	Coldest daily TX	Annual	Whole country
Amount of cool days	Percentage of days when TX < 10th percentile	Annual	Whole country
Amount of hot days	Percentage of days when TX > 90th percentile	Annual	Whole country
Amount of cold nights	Percentage of days when TN < 10th percentile	Annual	Whole country
Amount of warm nights	Percentage of days when TN > 90th percentile	Annual	Whole country

- **Departments and Stakeholders who decide on indicators:** South Africa Meteorological Office. Based upon the list of climate indicators from the World Meteorological Organization Expert Team on Climate Change Detection and Indices (ETCCDI).
- **Frequency of update:** Annually

❖ Maternal, newborn and child health indicators

Table 10: MNCH indicators, South Africa

Indicator	Definition	Frequency	Coverage
Antenatal 1 st visit (more or less than 20 weeks)	Antenatal visit before or after 20 weeks of gestation	Monthly	Local regions and national
Maternal Death	Death of the mother	Monthly	Local regions and national
Postnatal visit 6 days after delivery	Postnatal visit to a healthcare facility 6 days after delivery	Monthly	Local regions and national
Age of mother	Age of Mother	Monthly	Local regions and national
Mode of delivery	For example: Caesarean Section	Monthly	Local regions and national
Stillbirth	A baby who dies after 28 weeks of	Monthly	Local regions and national

Indicator	Definition	Frequency	Coverage
	pregnancy, but before or during birth		
Low Birth Weight Birth	Baby weighing less than 2500g	Monthly	Local regions and national
Death of baby in facility	Death of baby in facility 0 t 7 days and 7 to 28 days after birth.	Monthly	Local regions and national
HIV Positive Mother	The mother tests positive for HIV	Monthly	Local regions and national
HIV testing	testing of the baby at different time periods after birth.	Monthly	Local regions and national
Child Malnutrition	Malnutrition refers to deficiencies or excesses in nutrient intake, imbalance of essential nutrients or impaired nutrient utilisation. The double burden of malnutrition consists of both undernutrition and overweight and obesity, as well as diet-related noncommunicable diseases. Undernutrition manifests in four broad forms: wasting, stunting, underweight, and micronutrient deficiencies.	Monthly	Local regions and national
Child Mortality	Children 28 days to 11 years death by different causes such as malnutrition, infection and diarrhoea	Monthly	Local regions and national
Breastfeeding early start within 1 hour after birth	Breastfeeding early start within 1 hour after birth	Monthly	Local regions and national
School grade screening	How many learners were screened in each grade	Monthly	Local regions and national
School learner physical health	School referral for suspected TB, underweight,	Monthly	Local regions and national

Indicator	Definition	Frequency	Coverage
	overweight, deworming, oral health, eye care, hearing problems		
School learner mental health	School referral for phyco-social problems and mental health illness	Monthly	Local regions and national

- **Departments and Stakeholders who decide on indicators:** Department of Health and Department of Health and Education Department for Integrated School Health program.
- **Frequency of update:** Every 2 years

❖ Climate change and health indicators

Table 11 lists CCHI proposed by the climate and health committee in South Africa to be tracked in the future. There were extra CCHIs suggested but these are still under discussion.

Table 11: Climate change and health indicators, South Africa

Indicator	Definition	Frequency	Coverage
Child under 5 years severe acute malnutrition incidence	Children under 5 are newly diagnosed with severe acute malnutrition per 1000 children under 5 years in the population	Monthly	Local regions and national
Child under 5 years diarrhoea with dehydration incidence	Diarrhoea with dehydration in children under 5 years incidence rate	Monthly	Local regions and national
Moderate Acute Malnutrition in new under 5	Malnutrition refers to deficiencies or excesses in nutrient intake, imbalance of essential nutrients or impaired nutrient utilisation. The double burden of malnutrition consists of both undernutrition and overweight and	Monthly	Local regions and national

Indicator	Definition	Frequency	Coverage
	obesity, as well as diet-related noncommunicable diseases. Undernutrition manifests in four broad forms: wasting, stunting, underweight, and micronutrient deficiencies.		
School learning referred for underweight	Proportion of learners screened by a nurse in line with ISHP service package diagnosed as underweight (below 2SD but above 3SD)	Monthly	Local regions and national
Daily school attendance	Daily school attendance records	Monthly	Local regions and national
School learner referred for mental health or psychosocial support	School learner referred for mental health or psychosocial support	Monthly	Local regions and national
Cholera cases reported/notified	Monitors the incidences of cholera cases to ensure stability of cases. Salinity, sunlight and high temperature influences growth of cholera bacteria while rainfall influences its spread	Monthly	Local regions and national
Vector borne diseases	Malaria, West Nile virus, dengue fever and yellow fever	Monthly	Local regions and national
Emergency Medical Services (EMS) P1 urban response under 30/60 minutes rate	Emergency Medical Services (EMS) P1 urban response under 30/60 minutes rate	Monthly	Local regions and national

- **Departments and Stakeholders who decide on indicators:** Climate and Health committee.
- **Frequency of update:** Every 2 years

6 Discussion

- **What is the extent to which climate and health indicators respectively are already being monitored by countries?**

Our research based on a small sample reveals that many countries do not yet have official monitoring processes in place for CCHIs, this includes in Europe. Many countries were reliant on regional or global processes such as the Lancet Countdown for Climate Change and Health (Romanello et al., 2023). In addition, most researchers were not familiar with the climate and health indicators in their country.

Our results show that South Africa has a system in place for developing climate change and health indicators that other countries can take advantage of and adapt to their local contexts. This process is carried out by a climate and health committee, made up of stakeholders across different areas who propose and decide which CCHIs will be monitored by regions in the country.

In addition, the process of selecting and developing indicators for monitoring initiatives like those from the UN and The Lancet Countdown on Climate Change and Health involves several steps. Both organisations utilise expert committees to choose relevant indicators, which are categorised to ensure transparency and alignment with open data principles. The UN's indicators are typically based on aggregated country-level data, collected from UN agencies, and published annually. The Lancet Countdown, while following similar categories as the UN to maintain transparency, is more research focused having indicators that would not be able to be operationalised by current in-country monitoring. Its indicator development is funded by the philanthropy of the Wellcome Trust and are managed by working groups led by key figures employed through a competitive process, who then employ support staff. To introduce a new indicator in The Lancet Countdown, researchers must submit a white paper and demonstrate the indicator's feasibility at either a regional or global level. While both the UN and The

Lancet Countdown have parallel processes for developing indicators, there appears to be a lack of collaboration between them. This leads to potential inefficiencies and duplicative efforts, highlighting the need for better coordination to enhance progress rather than expending unnecessary resources.

Climate and health indicators are stated to be created “with the purpose of monitoring, tracking, and communication and supporting decision making processes” (Di Napoli et al., 2022). A follow-up from our research should be to explore the extent to which existing climate change and health indicators are effective, one aspect of this is the knowledge around their selection from both the policy and research worlds.

- **Are there any climate or health indicators that could easily be transformed into climate change and health indicators?**

From our mapping exercise we saw that there are many opportunities for the creation of CCHI from existing climate indicators and health indicators. We recommend that these are validated in unison with country discussions before then being operationalised by countries. For example, there are indicators from both the World Meteorological Organization and the World Health Organization that present an opportunity to be harmonised i.e. Percentage of days when maximum temperature exceeds the 90th percentile and number of stillbirths on those days compared to days outside of that period (Donat et al., 2013; Perkins & Alexander, 2013).

From our results we found that only UNICEF at the moment does have a CCHI for child health, which was recently developed (UNICEF, 2021). The identification of further indicators across MNCH is something that we will address as part of the HIGH Horizons project, this work includes involvement from UNICEF.

- **What is the governance structure and who is involved in the selection of climate change and health indicators?**

The governance structure of governmental departments and their cross-departmental work is key to the successful implementation of countries having operational CCHI. For example, a key barrier is where there is not a process in place for the meteorological and health ministries to work together, this was evident from workshops that took place as part of deliverable 4.1 (Brimicombe et al., 2024b).

A suggestion that came out of our deliverable 4.1, that we would like to reiterate was to look at the approach taken between agriculture and meteorological sectors and see how this can be applied and adapted for the health sector. For example, many of the co-production practices that are used to help farmers to work with climate services can be and are being used with health workers (Ariom et al., 2022). Assessing the gaps within current agricultural climate services presents opportunities to improve climate services in the health sector and transfer these successes back to agriculture (Vaughan et al., 2019).

At a more global level we observed that there are strengths and weaknesses of current approaches to select monitoring indicators. For UN there is a long-running process that has well documented success in being rolled out (UN Statistics Division, 2015). In the case of the Lancet Countdown this process is quicker than traditional indicator processes, less negotiations appear to be involved before an indicator is implemented. In all cases strengths and weaknesses can be suggested from who is involved in the process. For example, having a diverse representation of the global population is something that initiatives strive towards. As previously mentioned, our work here motivates us to take steps to better understand the implementation and monitoring of indicators as they become operational, we will update on this work in a future deliverable in August 2025.

➤ **Links with the wider work of HIGH Horizons**

HIGH Horizons is fortunate to have the WHO as a partner and benefits from the WHO Expert Group set up particularly to advise on and select MNCH indicators to track and monitor the impact of heat exposure.

In addition, as documented in D4.1 (Brimicombe et al., 2024b), there are country processes being spearheaded by our partners Wits RHI and CeSHHAR in South Africa and Zimbabwe respectively and which are progressing towards the selection and monitoring of CCHI for MNCH at country level. We have been in discussions to see if country workshops such as those conducted in South Africa and Zimbabwe and similar initiatives could be organised by other countries, preferably supported by the WHO Departments of Maternal, Newborn, Child and Adolescent Health and Ageing (WHO/MCA) and Climate Change and Health (WHO/CCH), and by the WHO Regional or Country Offices. There are also plans by HIGH Horizons partners to explore the attribution of heat exposure to maternal, newborn and child health, which can be seen as a future avenue for climate change and health indicator creation/selection, allowing several for example pre-term births to be attributed to climate change.

Other colleagues on HIGH Horizons have been engaging on the work of the DHS (Corsi et al., 2012) and how to best support them with integrating climate change within their surveys. We will update on the progress of all our efforts in future deliverables.

7 Summary

The study presented summarises key information on CCHIs in monitoring, tracking, and communicating the health impacts of climate change. These indicators can be used to support decision-making for developing, evaluating, and implementing intervention strategies and plans.

Five main summary themes arise from our findings.

1) Extent of Monitoring: While some countries have begun monitoring climate change and health indicators, many do not have official systems in place. South Africa's model of a dedicated climate and health committee could serve as a blueprint for other nations.

2) Transformation of Indicators: There is potential to transform existing climate and health indicators into more comprehensive metrics that integrate both aspects. This transformation should be explored experimentally before operational implementation. While UNICEF has identified CCHI for child health, the absence of CCHI for maternal and newborn health highlights the importance of the HIGH Horizons project's objectives. A consolidated and prioritised set across MNCH will be useful for countries.

3) Governance Structure: Effective governance structures are crucial for implementing and sustaining climate change and health indicators. Cross-departmental collaboration, particularly between meteorological and health ministries, is essential. This is an area that we will continue to explore.

4) International and National Initiatives: The study showed the importance of both international and national efforts in developing and implementing CCHIs. The WHO's Expert Group and the collaboration established by WHO with UNICEF, UNFPA and WMO as well as the related process for selecting climate change and health indicators are significant international efforts. National initiatives, such as those in South Africa and Zimbabwe, are also critical.

5) Future Directions: The study calls for further exploration of the use of existing climate change and health indicators and how this contributes to decision-making processes within countries and in international initiatives.

8 Conclusion

In this report, climate change and health indicators to track and monitor the impact of heat on maternal, newborn and child health were discussed. The background of the importance of indicators for heat exposure and maternal, newborn and child health was outlined in chapter 2. Then, in chapter 3 the methods for this report were discussed. An overview of climate change and health indicators was given in chapter 4. In chapter 5, national monitoring processes were outlined for five countries: Austria, Finland, Italy, South Africa and Zimbabwe. In chapter 6 we discussed the extent to which climate and health indicators respectively are already being monitored at country level, the potential for transforming known climate or health indicators into climate change and health indicators, and the governance structure and stakeholders required for the creation/selection of climate change and health indicators. Finally, a summary was provided in chapter 7.

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10 Annex

Template for national country climate and health indicators.

Country Name:

Name of those involved in filling in this template:

Climate Indicators:

Name of indicator (i.e. heatwave)	Definition	Unit of measure	Coverage in the country (i.e. local, regional, country level)

Departments and Stakeholders who decide on indicators:

How often are indicators updated?

How are new indicators suggested?

Maternal, Newborn and Child Health (MNCH) Indicators:

Name of indicator (i.e. heatwave)	Definition	Unit of measure	Coverage in the country (i.e. local, regional, country level)

Departments and Stakeholders who decide on indicators:

How often are indicators updated?

How are new indicators suggested?

Country Climate and Health Indicators:

Name of indicator (i.e. heatwave)	Definition	Unit of measure	Coverage in the country (i.e. local, regional, country level)

Departments and Stakeholders who decide on indicators:

How often are indicators updated?

How are new indicators suggested?

Any other information you would like to include about climate and/or health indicators?